

Estimating the Survival Time Until Development of Hypertension of Diabetes Mellitus Patients in Some Bayelsa State Hospitals in Nigeria

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 02 April 2026</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Juliana Iworikumo Consul</p>	<p>Introduction: In this research, the time until the development of hypertension among diabetes mellitus patients is estimated. This study has also identified the determinants of hypertension among the patients using a data set from two hospitals in Bayelsa state, Nigeria.</p> <p>Materials and Method: A sample of 206 subjects with diabetes mellitus were available for the research. The outcome variable or event of interest (survival time) which is the duration during which the diabetes subjects developed hypertension. The Kaplan Meier curve was used to estimate and plot the survival function. The Cox model was also used to explore the relationship between the survival of a subject and several predictor variables.</p> <p>Results: The median survival time to develop hypertension after diabetes diagnosis is approximately 56 months (4 years and 8 months). The underweight patients are having a superior survival to the other BMI categories as the graph of the underweight patients is consistently higher than the others. The Cox proportional test shows that there are highly significant effects of at least some predictor variables and the determinants of hypertension are age, type of job, income, BMI, salt intake and history of hypertension.</p> <p>Conclusion: This research concludes by recommending that diabetes patients should manage their blood sugar levels properly in order to lower the risk of hypertension and also patients should reduce the intake of salt, do regular physical activities which yields an acute lowering of blood pressure and manage their weight (BMI) to reduce the combined risk of diabetes and hypertension.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Determinants, Cox model, Survival function, Variables, Hazard function, Hypertension.</p>	

I. INTRODUCTION

Hypertension which is having blood pressure above normal is the most important modifiable risk factor for cardiovascular disease. It is commonly defined as a persistently increase in blood pressure in which systolic blood pressure reading (SBP) is greater than or equal to 140 mmHg and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) is greater than or equal to 90 mmHg (15). The incidence of hypertension is seriously increasing in most countries. Some of the risk factors include obesity, salt intake, physical inactivity etc. Diabetes mellitus is described as a metabolic disorder caused by either lack of insulin secretion, impaired insulin

action or both (11). The clinical diagnosis of diabetes mellitus has symptoms which depends on the duration and type of diabetes such as unexplained weight loss, increased thirst, recurrent infections, increased urine volume, drowsiness etc. The blood sugar level is categorized as normal: 70-99 mg/dL (3.9-5.5 mmol/L), prediabetes: 100-125 mg/dL (5.6-6.9 mmol/L), diabetes: ≥ 126 mg/dL (7.0 mmol/L) on multiple occasions and hypoglycemia (low) ≤ 7.0 mmol/L. Most People with diabetes mellitus are at increased risk of cardiovascular, peripheral vascular and cerebrovascular disease.

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The Comorbidity of hypertension and diabetes mellitus which is an individual is living with both high blood pressure and diabetes simultaneously is complex and associated with high risk of complications (5). The conditions of both hypertension and diabetes mellitus are closely intertwined as up to seventy five percent with diabetes also have hypertension (1). Both diseases share overlapping risk factors such as ethnicity, lifestyle determinants etc. and their coexistence significantly increase the damage of the heart, blood vessels, kidneys etc. and thereby creating a high- risk for cardiovascular disease and mortality.

This research is aimed at modelling the time until the development of hypertension among diabetes mellitus patients. It will also identify the determinants of hypertension among the patients using a data set from two hospitals in Bayelsa state, Nigeria being that to the best of our knowledge, no such study has been conducted in Yenagoa, Nigeria. (9) examined the factors associated with the control of blood pressure and the adherence to medical instructions among patients with hypertension emphasizing on nonlinear educational effects and subgroup differences by sex and comorbidity. Obesity is a significant health challenge that is linked to increased blood pressure and is estimated to account for 65 to 78 percent of the primary hypertension cases (12). However, the methods used to quantify body fat are not routinely available and so the body mass index (BMI) which is the weight (measured in kilograms) divided by height (measured in meters square) is the most commonly used metric for measuring obesity (3). The normal weight is defined as BMI: 18.5 – 24.9 kilograms / meters square, overweight as BMI: 25 – 29.9 kilograms / meters square and obesity as BMI: ≥ 30 kilograms / meters square (WHO, 1999)

(9) used a multistage random sampling design where participants were identified and questionnaires using multivariable logistic regression models were used to identify associated factors and restricted cubic spline and quadratic models.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Data collection

A total sample of 206 subjects were available for the research. The subjects in this study are patients with diabetes mellitus who were attending the certified diabetes education specialist clinic in two different public hospitals in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The subjects were followed for different periods during which some subjects developed hypertension. The period of follow up was for 84 months. The data were entered into notepad and analyzed using R statistical software.

B. Variables

The outcome variable or event of interest (survival time) is the duration during which the diabetes subjects developed

hypertension. This is measured in months from the date of treatment of diabetes started to the date of outcome or event of hypertension. The subject is considered to have had the event or had a failure time if he or she has developed hypertension in the follow-up period or otherwise censored (if the subject has not developed hypertension when the study ended). In this case, the data for the subjects is provided for a period of time prior to the occurrence of the event of interest before the end of the study or maybe due to lose of follow up. The data used in this study is the right censored (14).

The predictor variables used in this research were all grouped into categories are given as:

Age: Group “1” for ≤ 30 years, “2” for 31 to 40 years, “3” for 41 to 50 years, “4” for 51 to 60 years, “5” for 61 years and above.

Gender: Group “1” for male and “2” for female.

Marital status: Group “1” for single, “2” for married and “3” for divorced and “4” for widow/ widower.

Ethnicity: Group “1” for Ijaw, “2” for Isoko, “3” for Urhobo and “4” for others.

Religion: Group “1” for Christianity, “2” for Islam and “3” for others.

Educational level: Group “1” for No education, “2” for Primary, “3” for Secondary, “4” for Graduate and “5” for Post graduate.

Job type: Group “1” for farmer, “2” for civil servant, “3” for business and “4” for others.

Income level: Group “1” for \leq N50,000, “2” for N51,000 to N100,000, “3” for N101,000 to N150,000, “4” for N151,000 and above.

Status of smoking: Group “1” for smoker and “2” for non-smokers.

Status of drinking: Group “1” for alcohol drinker and “2” for non-alcohol drinker.

Physical activity: Group “1” for yes and “2” for no.

BMI: Group “1” for underweight (<18.5), “2” for normal ($18.5-22.9$), “3” for overweight ($23 - 24.9$) and “4” for (>25).

Salt intake: Group “1” for low, “2” for medium and “3” for high.

Family history of diabetes: Group “1” yes and “2” for no.

Family history of hypertension: Group “1” yes and “2” for no.

Censoring indicator: “1” if the subject had hypertension and “0” if the subject was censored.

C. Methodology

Survival analysis is the statistical methodology involving times of events of interest. In this study, the event of interest is the time until a diabetes patient develops hypertension. In cases where the subject has not developed hypertension when the study terminated at some specified time, a distinguishing universal feature of survival analysis known as right censoring was used. One main objective of the

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survival analysis is to estimate and plot the survival function.

The survival function which is defined as the probability that a subject survives beyond a given time (8). The hazard function which is defined as the instantaneous rate at which events occur for subjects which are surviving at a given time. (8) introduced the relevant concepts and meanings of the survival analysis method and used the hazard rate function, cumulative distribution function, survival function, and cumulative hazard rate function to describe the concept of survival time with applications to various industries. It is necessary to note that the higher the hazard rate, the lower the survival time.

One of the most widely used method for calculating or estimating and plotting the survival function is by using the Kaplan Meier curve. The Kaplan Meier method is a non-parametric method that do not make any assumptions about the distribution of the survival times of the subjects in the study (7).

Another objective of the survival analysis is to compare the survival times of two or more groups. This is also the same as testing whether two groups of survival data are from a common survival function. The Log-rank test is used in this case (4).

The Cox model is a statistical technique for exploring the relationship between the survival of a subject and several predictor variables. This model allows us to estimate the hazard (or risk) of death for a subject, given the predictor variables. (2) proposed using the proportional hazards as one way of incorporating predictor variables in a model. The plausibility of the assumption of the proportional hazard could be checked either graphically (using Schoenfeld residuals) which is usually implemented using statistical softwares or by including a time-dependent effect and examining its significance.

III. RESULTS

Very few 9(4.36%) of the subjects were less than 30. Most 79(38.35%) of the subjects were between the ages of 51 to 60 years. The number of males in the study were slightly above half 111(53.88%) of the subjects. Majority 131 (63.59%) of the subjects were married. Most 158 (76.70%) were from the Ijaw ethnicity. Nearly all 194 (94.17%) of the subjects were Christians. Very few 5 (2.43%) of the subjects were illiterates. Majority 137 (66.50%) of the subjects were civil servants. Regarding the income of the subjects, above half 110 (53.40) earned between N51,000 and N100,000. Majority 194 (94.17%) were non-smokers. Also, about half 108 (52.43%) of the subjects were drink alcohol. Most 180 (87.38%) of the subjects do not engage in physical activity. Above half 118 (57.28%) of the subjects were overweighted. Very low number 30 (14.56%) of the subjects had high salt intake. Majority 192 (93.20%) and 148 (71.84%) of the

subjects had history of diabetes and hypertension respectively.

D. Survival analysis of the time from the diagnosis of diabetes to the development of hypertension

The Kaplan Meier estimate of the survival distribution for the time until the development of hypertension data was calculated using the R statistical software without assuming any particular model and the plot is shown in Figure 1. During the time of follow-up time, 181 (87.86%) subjects developed hypertension. Figure I shows the Kaplan Meier estimate of the survival function. The broken lines in Figure I show a point-wise 95% confidence interval around the survival function.

The median survival time of the 206 subjects was 56 months. This gives the maximum time for which the survival estimate is 0.5 or higher. At 56 months half of the subjects have experienced the event. A survival probability of 0.824 at 43 months means that there is 82.4% chance of a diabetic patient remaining without having hypertension at 43 months.

Figure I: Kaplan-Meier estimate of the survival function

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Figure II: shows the plot of survival probability against time of underweight, normal weight, overweight and obese patients.

From Figure II, the plot of survival probability against time of underweight, normal, overweight and obese show that the underweight patients are having a superior survival to the other BMI categories as the graph of the underweight patients is consistently higher than the others.

Cox proportional fit test

A Cox proportional hazards fit, using all predictor variables gave the results in Table I.

Table I: Cox Proportional fit test of all predictor variables

<i>Sn</i>	<i>Variables</i>	<i>Coef</i>	<i>Exp(Coef)</i>	<i>P value</i>
1.	Age	0.665	0.513	0.098
2.	Gender	0.079	1.082	0.1738
3.	Marital	0.038	0.962	0.1647
4.	Ethnicity	0.015	0.985	0.094
5.	Religion	0.169	1.184	0.292
6.	Educational level	0.050	1.051	0.090
7.	Job	0.260	0.771	0.121
8.	Income	0.277	0.758	0.088
9.	Smoking	0.158	1.170	0.503
10.	Alcohol	0.184	0.832	0.191
11.	Physical activity	0.373	1.452	0.315
12.	BMI	0.449	1.567	0.106
13.	Salt intake	0.465	1.593	0.182
14.	History of diabetes	0.422	1.525	0.373
15.	History of hypertension	0.659	0.518	0.303

The Cox proportional test shows that there are highly significant effects of at least some predictor variables with p-value=0. By inspection, the predictor variables age, type of job, income, BMI, salt intake and history of hypertension are significant. Gender, marital status, ethnicity, religion, educational level, status of smoking, status of alcohol, physical activity and history of diabetes seem not to be so important.

Being a female increases the risk of being hypertensive by 8%. Age is slightly significant. Decreasing age leads to reduced risk of being hypertensive at a rate of about 51% a year. Being a smoker increases the risk of being hypertensive by 17%. BMI is slightly significant. Moving from one category from BMI to the next category increases the risk of being hypertensive by 56%. Therefore, obese

diabetes patient has 56% increased risk of being hypertensive than a normal weight patient.

Increasing the salt intake level from low to medium increases the risk of being hypertensive by 59%. A family history of hypertension is a significant predictor variable and has the risk of developing hypertension at a rate of 52%.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this research, the time until the development of hypertension among diabetes mellitus patients is estimated using a sample data set of 206 patients from two hospitals in Bayelsa state, Nigeria. The Kaplan Meier curve was used to estimate the median survival time to develop hypertension after being diagnosed of diabetes was also estimated. The study reveals the significant proportion of time to develop hypertension within the time of the diagnosis of diabetes.

The Cox model was used to explore the relationship between the survival of a subject and several predictor variables and the determinants of hypertension among the patients were identified. The development of hypertension is very much accelerated by age, the intake of salt, type of job, income, BMI and history of hypertension. Gender, marital status, ethnicity, religion, educational level, status of smoking, status of alcohol, physical activity and history of diabetes seem not to be so important.

Diabetes mellitus leads to high blood pressure through increased sodium retention and stimulation of the nervous system. Additionally, insulin resistance which is common in diabetes mellitus is known to act as a catalyst which develops hypertension. The coexistence of diabetes and hypertension is dangerous, as it increases the risk of the likelihood of heart failure, stroke, kidney diseases etc. and early mortality compared to having either diabetes or hypertension. This coexistence could also lead to high rates of blindness and damage of the nerve if not managed properly. Combining both diseases increases diminish the quality of life.

This research recommends that diabetes patients should manage their blood sugar levels properly in order to lower the risk of hypertension. It also recommends that patients should reduce the intake of salt, do regular physical activities which yields an acute lowering of blood pressure and manage their weight (BMI) to reduce the combined risk of diabetes and hypertension. Patients are also advised to adhere to strict medication for effective management of hypertension and time until the development is delayed.

The research is not only important to the patients, individuals and the general public health system but it will have great economic influence as a significant proportion of the population that are supposed to be productive may become chronically ill and thereby exposing their families to poverty.

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